

Complexes of 4n-Butyl-4H-1,2,4-triazole with Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II)

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The complexes of Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II) chlorides with 4n-butyl-4H-1,2,4-triazole have been prepared and characterized on the basis of analytical, magnetic susceptibility and infrared data. The ligand shows bidentate behaviour in all the complexes except those of Cd(II) and Hg(II), where it acts as a monodentate ligand also.

THE complexes of 3 or 5 substituted 1,2,4-triazoles with metal ions have been studied as regards bonding and structure¹⁻⁶. The compound 4n-butyl-4H-1,2,4-triazole having structure (I) contains nitrogen as donor atoms. It is a systemic protectant fungicide against leaf rust for both spring and winter wheat. The parent compound falls in the class of the aromatic heterocyclics and its unique structure is discussed with reference to pyridine and pyrrole to which triazole is structurally related. The N-1 and N-2 nitrogens of triazole are aptly termed as the pyridine nitrogens, while the N-4 nitrogen is called the pyrrole nitrogen. So it can act as a bidentate ligand through both the nitrogens present at N-1 and N-2. It will, therefore, be of interest to investigate the nature of bonding in the complexes formed by 4n-butyl-4H-1,2,4-triazole. In this paper, the synthesis and structural aspects of the complexes of Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II) chlorides with 4n-butyl-4H-1,2,4-triazole are reported.

Experimental

All chemicals used for the preparation of the complexes are of "AnalaR" or "Chemically Pure" grade. The ligand is 4n-butyl-4H-1,2,4-triazole, hereafter denoted as RH-124.

Preparation of complexes: The complexes were prepared by dropwise adding 0.01 mole of chloride of the metal in minimum quantity of absolute alcohol to 10 ml of RH-124 (70%) solution with

constant stirring. The mixture was heated on a water bath to concentrate. It was cooled and solvent ether was added to separate the solid complex which was dried under vacuum. The analysis for metal and chloride was done by standard methods⁷.

The ir spectra (nujol mull) were obtained using Perkin-Elmer Infrared spectrometer, Model-621. Magnetic susceptibility data for the complexes were obtained using Gouy method.

Results and Discussion

The magnetic and spectral properties of manganese, cobalt, nickel, copper, zinc, cadmium and mercury complexes were studied to understand the spatial arrangement of ligand molecules around the central metal ions. The analytical results are in agreement with general formulae of the metal complexes given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY AND OTHER DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compound	Colour	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	Found %		Required %	
			Metal	Chlorine	Metal	Chlorine
MnR ₂ Cl ₂	White	5.82	11.40	14.30	11.00	14.17
CoR ₂ Cl ₂	Light pink	4.40	11.56	14.65	11.66	14.06
NiR ₂ Cl ₂	Violet	3.03	9.14	11.92	9.37	11.27
CuR ₂ Cl ₂	Blue	1.65	12.76	14.20	12.47	13.94
ZnR ₂ Cl ₂	White	Diamag.	12.70	14.01	12.08	13.88
CdR ₂ Cl ₂	White	Diamag.	13.67	9.42	13.91	8.78
HgR ₂ Cl ₂	White	Diamag.	19.80	7.13	19.61	6.94

The compounds of RH-124 with metal ions are insoluble in water, alcohol, acetone, benzene, chloroform, dioxane, ether and nitrobenzene. The insolubility of the complexes in different solvents indicates that they are polymeric in nature. The polymeric nature of these complexes agrees with the already reported complexes of 1,3,4-triazole-5-(5)-thiol which are polymeric⁸. The electrical conductance could not be recorded due to insolubility in different solvents.

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Infrared spectra : The major ir bands of the ligand and the complexes are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—IR SPECTRAL DATA OF RH-124 AND THOSE OF COMPLEXES (cm⁻¹) IN NUJOL MULL

Compound	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ cm ⁻¹	$\nu(\text{N}-\text{N})$ cm ⁻¹	$\nu(\text{C}-\text{N})$ ring cm ⁻¹	$\nu(\text{C}-\text{N})$ aliphatic cm ⁻¹
4n-butyl-4H-1,2,4-triazole (RH-124)	1602	1472	1362	1180
Mn(II) complex	1547	1448	1373	1200
Co(II) "	1550	1450	1375	1206
Ni(II) "	1550	1448	1375	1208
Cu(II) "	1550	1450	1375	1210
Zn(II) "	1648	1450	1372	1190
Cd(II) "	1645	1449	1375	1203
	1545		1350	
Hg(II) "	1550	1448	1370	1180
	1585		1317	

The ir spectrum of the ligand shows four absorption bands at 1602, 1472, 1362 and 1180 cm⁻¹. The sharp absorption at 1602 cm⁻¹ in the spectrum of RH-124 has been assigned to C=N vibration. The medium absorption at 1472 cm⁻¹ may be due to partial contribution from $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ and main contribution from N-N vibration. The absorption due to mixed contribution of $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$, $\nu(\text{N}-\text{N})$, $\delta(\text{N}-\text{H})$ and $\delta(\text{C}-\text{H})$ has been reported to appear at 1460 cm⁻¹ in the case of 1,2,4-triazole-3(5)-thiol and at 1470 cm⁻¹ in the deuterated derivative⁶. This supports that the present assignment is correct. The sharp absorption at 1362 cm⁻¹ has been assigned to C-N vibration (ring). There appears a weak absorption at 1180 cm⁻¹ which may be due only to N-C vibration of the group $\text{>N}-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_3$ along with the contribution of $\delta\text{C}-\text{H}$ vibrations.

The important infrared absorption peaks of the Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) complexes were compared with those of the pure ligand in nujol mull. The first band assigned to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ and the second band to $\nu(\text{N}-\text{N})$ appear at lower frequencies in the case of the spectra of complexes. There was no split in the band due to C=N absorption on complexation as there was only one peak for the same in the spectrum of each complex. This indicates that the coordination is not through one pyridine nitrogen of the ring as the coordination through one of these nitrogens requires a split in the peak due to C=N absorption. This suggests that the ligand is coordinated to two different metal ions through both the nitrogen atoms at positions 1 and 2 of the group, because the coordination of both the nitrogen atoms to the same metal ion is not possible due to the presence of strain in three membered rings. The coordination of different metal ions leads to the polymeric nature of the complex. The positive shift in $\nu(\text{C}-\text{N})$ ring and $\nu(\text{C}-\text{N})$ aliphatic indicates that pyrrole nitrogen is not coordinated. It is also according to expectation, because of blocking by the bulky C₄H₉ group.

There are two peaks due to C=N stretching vibrations in the spectra of Cd(II) and Hg(II) complexes. The first may be due to the C=N vibration of the group the nitrogen of which is uncoordinated, while the second may be due to C=N vibration of the group the nitrogen of which is coordinated. The peak due to N-N stretching appearing at lower value indicates coordination of the ligand through the nitrogen of group N-N. There are two peaks due to the C-N vibration (in the ring) i.e. the vibration of the group :

The presence of two peaks again supports the conclusion that the coordination is through one nitrogen of the group =N-N=. The absorption at higher frequency than the absorption for the same group in the case of free ligand supports the uncoordinated behaviour of pyrrole nitrogen linked to butyl group. The second peak is lower but it cannot be properly explained. One can, however, say that the peak is due to C-N vibration of the group $\text{-N}=\text{CH}-\text{N}<$, the pyridine nitrogen of which is uncoordinated.

The C-N vibration of the group $\text{>N}-\text{C}_4\text{H}_9$ (outside ring) is higher than that in spectrum of pure ligand. This also reveals the uncoordinated nature of the pyrrole nitrogen and indirectly supports the coordination through one of the pyridine nitrogen of the group. It was concluded on the basis of ir data that the bonding is through the pyridine nitrogen of the triazole ring. It behaves as bidentate in Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) complexes whereas in Cd(II) and Hg(II) it behaves both as bidentate as well as monodentate ligands.

Magnetic susceptibility studies :

Mn(II) complex : The magnetic susceptibility measurements give the magnetic moment value of 5.82 B.M. (Table 1) at room temperature (24.5°) for the complex $(\text{RH}-124)_2\text{MnCl}_2$. This value of magnetic moment reveals the presence of five unpaired electrons thereby showing that the complex is of high spin type.

Co(II) complex : The complex has magnetic moment value of 4.40 B.M. which indicates the spin free nature of the complex. It also shows the presence of three unpaired electrons. The high spin octahedral Co(II) complexes have magnetic moments ranging from 4.7-5.2 B.M. and the tetrahedral complexes generally have magnetic moments in the range 4.1-4.8 B.M. These complexes have higher magnetic moment values due to the high orbital contribution when it is considered in the relation, $\mu_{\text{eff}} = [4S(S+1) + L(L+1)]^{\frac{1}{2}}$.

The magnetic moment is expected to be 5.2 B.M. and its value for the octahedral complexes should lie in the range 3.88-5.2 B.M. However, the orbital contribution to the magnetic moment depends upon the amount of L remaining associated with the ground state⁹. It has been found that the magnetic moments in the case of octahedral cobalt(II) complexes lie in the range 4.8-5.2 B.M.

The infrared absorption spectra have shown that the ligand is bonded to the metal ion through two nitrogen atoms. This shows that Co(II) ions are bridged through the nitrogen atoms of the RH-124 in order to acquire the distorted octahedral stereochemistry about the metal atom.

Ni(II) complex: The magnetic moment value of 3.07 B.M. at room temperature (24.5°) for the complex (RH-124)₂NiCl₂ suggests the presence of two unpaired electrons which reveals the spin-free nature of the complex. This rules out the possibility of square planar configuration which requires the complex to be diamagnetic. The tetrahedral complexes of Ni(II) have the ground term ³T₁ which has nearly a full orbital contribution varying with temperature. Most of the tetrahedral complexes of Ni(II) show μ_{eff} in the range 3.2-4.0 B.M. at room temperature. The octahedral Ni(II) complexes has ground term ⁶A₁ which makes no orbital contribution. But the excited states ³T₂ and ³T₁ mix into the ground term ⁶A₁ and due to this reason, there is orbital contribution to the magnetic moment. Usually the octahedral Ni(II) complexes have magnetic moment in the range 2.8-3.3 B.M. for high spin octahedral complexes of Ni(II) depending upon the orbital contribution¹⁰. The value in the present case is well within the range of 2.8-3.3 B.M. So the complex may have octahedral stereochemistry.

Cu(II) complex: The magnetic moment for the complex (RH-124)₂CuCl₂ has been found to be 1.65 B.M. This value corresponds to the presence of one unpaired electron in the complex. The low value of μ_{eff} as compared to the expected spin only value of 1.73 B.M. may be due to polymeric nature of the complex.

It has been confirmed on the basis of magnetic susceptibility that the complexes of Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) are spin free. The octahedral stereochemistry has been suggested for these complexes. The complexes of Zn(II), Cd(II), Hg(II) are diamagnetic. However, the possibility of octahedral stereochemistry in the case of Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II) complexes may not be ruled out.

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References

1. M. R. GAJENDRAGAD and U. AGARWALA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1976, **37**, 2429.
2. M. R. GAJENDRAGAD and U. AGARWALA *Z. anorg. allg. Chem.*, 1975, **415**, 84.
3. M. R. GAJENDRAGAD and U. AGARWALA, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1975, **28**, 763.
4. I. P. KHULLAR and U. AGARWALA, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1976, **28**, 1529.
5. U. AGARWALA and B. SINGH, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1969, **7**, 728.
6. B. K. GUPTA, D. S. GUPTA, S. K. DIKSHIT and U. AGARWALA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1977, **15A**, 624.
7. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Chemistry", Longmans, New York, 1961, pp. 480, 493, 497, 524, 528, 538.
8. B. N. FIGGIS and R. S. NYHOLM, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 12.
9. B. N. FIGGIS and J. LEWIS, *Progr. Inorg. Chem.*, 1964, **6**, 37.
10. A. EARNSHAW, "Introduction to Magneto-Chemistry", Academic Press, London and New York, 1968, p. 35.